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S1: Sample description including analytic subsamples

Supplementary Table 1 summarizes the available sample for each analysis, which varies depending on the availability of electrode impedance measures and the identification of artifacts. In general, the main dataset provided more complete data coverage than the validation dataset.

Supplementary Table 1

Participant demographic characteristics of the full sample and analytic subsamples

	Main dataset			Validation dataset		
	N	mean age (sd)	sex (m/f)	N	mean age (sd)	sex (m/f)
Total	89	22.9 (3.8)	22/67	93	23.8 (3.0)	22/67
Per analysis						
Electrode impedance	89	22.9 (3.8)	22/67	55	23.2 (2.3)	28/27
Algorithmic quality metrics	89	22.9 (3.8)	22/67	93	23.8 (3.0)	36/57
Component retention: Ocular artifacts	88	23.0 (3.8)	22/66	93	23.8 (3.0)	36/57
Component retention: Muscular artifacts	86	22.9 (3.8)	21/65	93	23.8 (3.0)	36/57
Component retention: Cardiac artifacts	56	23.0 (3.6)	14/42	35	23.6 (2.8)	21/14
Incremental contamination: Blink artifacts	76	22.8 (3.8)	17/59	86	23.9 (3.0)	33/53
Incremental contamination: Saccade artifacts	55	23.3 (4.1)	18/37	57	24.31 (3.1)	22/35
Incremental contamination: Muscular artifacts (EEG)	63	22.2 (3.5)	13/50	69	23.9 (3.1)	25/44
Incremental contamination: Muscular artifacts (EMG)	75	22.9 (3.8)	18/57	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

Note: Muscular artifact detection based on EMG data was not applicable (n.a.) to the validation dataset as no EMG channels were collected during its data acquisition.

S2. Number of independent components and data segments of each artifact category per participant

Supplementary Figure 1 visualizes the number of independent components available per participant for the component retention approach. Participants showing zero components of a target artifact category were excluded from this specific analysis.

Supplementary Figure 1: Number of independent components reflecting the three different artifact categories (ocular, muscular, cardiac) as labeled by ICLabel.

Supplementary Figure 2 visualizes the number of available data segments per participant for the incremental contamination approach.

Supplementary Figure 2: Number of detected eye artifacts (annotated by the eye tracker) and data segments available for the incremental contamination approach investigating ocular contamination (row A and C) and muscular contamination effects (row B and D). Note that one-second segments were epoched around each detected eye artifact and could thus be overlapping in time. Subsequently, one, three or five of these segments were randomly selected. For visualization purposes, two outliers showing more than 100 saccades, as well as two outliers showing more than 100 blinks were removed.

S3. Side by side visualizations

Supplementary Figures 3-6 visualize all main results (i.e. influence of data quality, ocular, muscular and cardiac artifacts on the aperiodic parameters) for both datasets for direct visual comparison. Note that statistical results are described in detail in the main manuscript (Table 1 and 2).

Supplementary Figure 3: Side by side visualization of data quality influences on the aperiodic parameters in both datasets. Panels A-H illustrate effects of electrode impedances on the aperiodic offset and exponent. Panels A&B show the topographical distribution of the aperiodic offset, exponent, and the impedances of each dataset. Panels C, E, F&H display standardized β 's from linear regressions predicting the aperiodic parameters from electrode impedances, green dots mark significant electrode clusters by the CBPT. Panel D&G present median-split aperiodic spectra at electrode Oz, shaded areas indicate standard error of the mean. Panels I-L depict the effects of algorithmic quality metrics (OHA THV, CHV) on the aperiodic parameters. Topographies show standardized β coefficients, with green dots indicating significant electrodes of the CBPTs. Scatterplots

below display average aperiodic parameters (across electrodes) as a function of the quality metrics, with dark blue lines representing least-squares fits.

Supplementary Figure 4: Side by side visualization of ocular artifact influences on the aperiodic parameters in both datasets. Panels A-F illustrate findings from the component retention approach. Small topographies on top of A, C, D&F display aperiodic parameters derived from fully cleaned data (all artifactual ICs removed) and partially cleaned (ocular IC's retained) data. Larger maps display standardized regression coefficients from linear mixed-effects models predicting aperiodic signal parameters from ocular contamination; green dots mark electrodes significant in CBPT. Panel B&E show average aperiodic spectra for fully cleaned versus ocular contaminated data, with shaded areas indicating standard error of the mean. Panels G-R present results from the incremental contamination approach for blinks and saccades, using the same visualization schemes as A-F. Contamination effects are illustrated by contrasting clean data (0 artifactual segments) vs. medium contaminated data (3 out of 15 artifactual segments).

Supplementary Figure 5: Side by side visualization of muscular artifact influences on the aperiodic parameters in both datasets. Panels A-F illustrate findings from the component retention approach. Small topographies on top of A, C, D&F display aperiodic parameters derived from fully cleaned data (all artifactual ICs removed) and partially cleaned (muscular IC's retained) data. Larger maps display standardized regression coefficients from linear mixed-effects models predicting aperiodic signal parameters from ocular contamination; green dots mark electrodes significant in CBPT. Panel B&E show average aperiodic spectra for fully cleaned versus ocular contaminated data, with shaded areas indicating standard error of the mean. Panel G-L present results from the incremental contamination approach for blinks and saccades, using the same visualization schemes as A-F. Contamination effects are illustrated by contrasting clean data (0 artifactual segments) vs. medium contaminated data (3 out of 15 artifactual segments).

Main dataset

Validation dataset

Supplementary Figure 6: Side by side visualization of cardiac artifact influences on the aperiodic parameters in both datasets from the component retention approach (Note that small topographies on top of A, C, D&F display aperiodic parameters derived from fully cleaned data (all artifactual ICs removed) and partially cleaned (cardiac IC's retained) data. Larger maps display standardized regression coefficients from linear mixed-effects models predicting aperiodic signal parameters from ocular contamination; green dots mark electrodes significant in CBPT. Panel B&E show average aperiodic spectra for fully cleaned versus ocular contaminated data, with shaded areas indicating standard error of the mean.

S4. Component retention approach: Ocular artifact removal in eyes open data

Applying the component retention approach to eyes open resting state data yielded highly significant results of ocular contamination on the aperiodic offset, with large standardized beta estimates, averaged across all significant electrodes (main dataset: avg $\beta = 0.73$, $p < 0.001$; validation dataset: avg $\beta = 0.97$, $p < 0.001$). Similar effects were observed on the aperiodic exponent (main dataset: avg $\beta = 0.72$, $p < 0.001$; validation dataset: avg $\beta = 0.90$, $p < 0.001$). Supplementary Figure 7 visualizes these results for both datasets.

Supplementary Figure 7: Component retention approach on ocular artifacts applied to eyes open resting state data. Small topographies on top of A&C display aperiodic parameters derived from fully cleaned data (all artifactual ICs removed) and partially cleaned, contaminated (ocular ICs retained) data. Larger maps display standardized regression coefficients from linear mixed-effects models predicting aperiodic signal parameters from ocular contamination; green dots mark electrodes significant in CBPT. Panel B shows mean aperiodic spectra for fully cleaned versus ocular contaminated data, with shaded areas indicating standard error of the mean. Panels D-F visualize the results for the validation dataset accordingly.

S5. Incremental contamination approach applied to fully cleaned data

Applying the incremental contamination approach to the fully cleaned data (i.e., after removing all artifact-related ICs) yielded smaller effect sizes than those reported in the main manuscript, where ICs of the target artifact category were retained. However, all effects remained statistically significant.

For ocular artifacts, both blink- and saccade-related contamination produced comparable results. For blinks, moderate effects were observed for the aperiodic offset when averaging across the electrodes of the largest significant cluster, with the standardized regression coefficient (β) reflecting the contrast between medium contamination (3 of 15 segments contaminated) and clean segments (main dataset: avg. $\beta = 0.24$, $p < 0.001$; validation dataset: avg. $\beta = 0.20$, $p < 0.001$). Similar effects were observed for the aperiodic exponent (main dataset: $p = 0.005$, avg. $\beta = 0.20$; validation dataset: avg. $\beta = 0.19$, $p = 0.003$).

The saccade-related results followed the same pattern, showing smaller effects on the aperiodic offset (main dataset: avg. $\beta = 0.08$, $p < 0.001$; validation dataset: avg. $\beta = 0.09$, $p < 0.001$) and on the aperiodic exponent (main dataset: avg. $\beta = 0.09$, $p = 0.017$; validation dataset: avg. $\beta = 0.09$, $p = 0.019$).

For muscular artifacts, no significant effects were observed on the aperiodic offset. However, the aperiodic exponent showed highly similar effects as reported in the main manuscript. Here, after removal of all muscular ICs, highly significant effects were observed in both datasets (main dataset, EMG-based detection: $p < 0.001$, avg. $\beta = -0.14$; main dataset, EEG-based detection: avg. $\beta = -0.20$, $p < 0.001$; validation dataset, EEG-based detection: avg. $\beta = -0.17$, $p < 0.001$).

Supplementary Figure 8: Effect of ocular artifacts on aperiodic parameters based on the incremental contamination approach applied to fully cleaned data (i.e. after removal of all ICs classified as ocular activity). Left column (A/D/G/J) visualizes standardized beta estimates predicting the aperiodic offset by blink and saccade contamination across the scalp, green electrodes highlight significant electrodes in the CBPTs. Here, the contamination effect is visualized by the contrast “clean data” (0 artifactual segments) vs. “medium contaminated data” (3 out of 15 artifactual segments). The right column (C/F/I/L) visualizes the effects on the aperiodic exponent accordingly. The middle column (B/E/H/K) shows average aperiodic spectra for clean or low/medium/high contaminated data (1/3/5 artifactual segments). Shaded error bars represent standard errors of the mean.

S6. Incremental contamination approach: EEG-based muscle detection in main dataset

Supplementary Figure 10 visualizes the results of the incremental contamination approach applied to muscular artifact contamination, employing EEG-based artifact classification in the main dataset. Note that the statistical results are reported in the main manuscript (Table 2).

Supplementary Figure 10: Effects of incremental muscular artifact contamination on the aperiodic parameters, with EEG-based muscular artifact detection in the main dataset. Small topographies in A and C display aperiodic parameters derived from clean or partially contaminated data. Larger maps show standardized regression coefficients from the linear mixed effects models predicting the aperiodic parameters from muscular contamination; green dots indicate electrodes significant in CBPT. The contamination effects are illustrated by contrast clean data (0 artifactual segments) vs. medium contaminated data (3 out of 15 artifactual segments). Panel B shows mean aperiodic spectra for the clean and partially contaminated data, with shaded areas indicating the standard errors of the mean.

S7. Detailed preprocessing pipelines

In a first step, error-prone channels were automatically identified and removed using the eeglab plugin `clean_rawdata` (http://sccn.ucsd.edu/wiki/Plugin_list_process). Channels were flagged for removal if any of the following criteria were met: a correlation coefficient below 0.85 when compared with an estimate derived from neighboring electrodes; line noise levels exceeding those of all other channels by more than 4 standard deviations; or the presence of a flat-line period longer than 5 seconds. The error-prone electrodes were interpolated using a spherical spline interpolation (EEGLAB function `eeg_interp.m`) at the end of the preprocessing pipeline before the automatic quality assessment of the EEG files (see below). Data were then high-pass filtered (-6 dB cutoff at 0.5 Hz) and processed with Zapline ([de Cheveigné, 2020](#)) to eliminate 50Hz line noise artifacts by removing seven power line components. Next, independent component analysis (ICA) was performed on a temporarily high-pass filtered version of the data (-6 dB cutoff at 1 Hz). All components were evaluated using the pre-trained ICLabel classifier ([Pion-Tonachini et al., 2019](#)), which assigns probability scores for line noise, channel noise, muscular activity, ocular activity, cardiac artifacts, brain, and other categories. Rather than immediately removing components with high artifact probabilities, we retained this information for later stages of the analysis pipeline, where we either preserved specific artifact components or excluded all artifactual components (see Figure 1 for an overview). For the subsequent automated quality assessment, however, components with artifact probabilities exceeding 0.8 for line noise, channel noise, muscular activity, ocular activity, or cardiac artifacts were temporarily removed. This temporary removal ensured that quality ratings were based on fully preprocessed data and not confounded by residual artifacts. Each EEG file was then evaluated according to four criteria: a file was marked as bad and excluded from further analysis if (1) more than 20% of the data points had amplitudes exceeding 20 μV , (2) over 35% of time points showed a variance greater than 10 μV across channels, (3) 35% or more of the electrodes exhibited high variance ($>10 \mu\text{V}$), or (4) the overall ratio of excluded electrodes exceeded 0.3

After these preprocessing steps, channels positioned outside the standard scalp montage were removed in the validation dataset: These included 10 electrodes placed on the face (primarily recording EOG activity) and 13 electrodes positioned on the chin and neck, which capture minimal brain activity. This resulted in 105 EEG channels in the validation dataset for subsequent analysis. For the main dataset, no channels were removed as it contained 128 standard scalp EEG channels. Finally, the data were re-referenced to a common average reference.

S8. Specparam model fits per analysis

Because each analysis type used a specific subsample of the data (and varying degree of artifact contamination), the model fits of the Specparam algorithm were evaluated separately and are presented in Supplementary Table 2. Note that for the electrode impedance based analysis of data quality in the validation dataset, a smaller subsample was available, however, the same average aperiodic fit and standard deviation were observed. Importantly, also for the incremental contamination analysis, in which the PSD is estimated based on 15 one-second segments, very high model fits were obtained. When further dividing this into the sub analysis of no / low / medium / high contamination, no systematic differences in specparam fits were observed.

Supplementary Table 2

Average model fits of the specparam algorithm for each analysis subtype

	Main dataset: Mean specparam fit R^2 (sd)	Validation dataset: Mean specparam fit R^2 (sd)
Data quality and component retention approach (all artifact ICs removed)	0.99 (0.01)	0.99 (0.02)
Component retention approach: Ocular artifacts retained	0.99 (0.01)	0.99 (0.02)
Component retention approach: Muscular artifacts retained	0.99 (0.03)	0.98 (0.03)
Component retention approach: Cardiac artifacts retained	0.99 (0.01)	0.99 (0.01)
Incremental contamination approach: Blink artifacts	0.96 (0.07)	0.96 (0.06)
Incremental contamination approach: Saccade artifacts	0.96 (0.07)	0.96 (0.06)
Incremental contamination approach: Muscular artifacts	0.97 (0.05)	0.96 (0.06)

S9. Distribution of impedances and algorithmic quality metrics

Supplementary Figure 11 visualizes the distribution of electrode impedances (across all electrodes and participant) and algorithmic quality metrics. Only impedance values within the ranges used for the analyses are included in the plots (Main dataset: 0-20 kOhm, Validation dataset:0-50kOhm).

Supplementary Figure 11: Distribution of electrode impedances and algorithmic quality measures (overall high amplitude, OHA; timepoints of high variance, THV; channels of high variance, CHV) in each dataset.

S10. Relation between algorithmic quality metrics and electrode impedances

The relationship between the investigated quality measures are depicted in Supplementary Table 3. Electrode impedances were not significantly related to any of the algorithmic quality metrics in both datasets. In contrast, the three different algorithmic quality metrics were all highly related to each other.

Supplementary Table 3

Pearson correlations between the algorithmic quality metric and impedance measures

	Impedances: $r(p)$	OHA: $r(p)$	THV: $r(p)$
OHA	0.08 (0.44) / -0.03 (0.85)		
THV	0.17 (0.10) / -0.06 (0.66)	0.70 (<0.001) / 0.97 (<0.001)	
CHV	-0.02 (0.86) / -0.03 (0.86)	0.83 (<0.001) / 0.91 (<0.001)	0.73 (<0.001) / 0.83 (<0.001)

Note: Impedances are averaged across all electrodes.

S11. Muscular artifact detection algorithm

The EEG-based muscular artifact detection algorithm was adapted from a previous approach by Gerla et al. (2017), combined with the automated muscular artifact detection algorithm implemented in MNE-Python (Gramfort, 2013). Following Gerla et al. (2017), PCA was applied to all EEG channels and the first principal component time series was extracted for further analyses, as this component typically contains high amplitude artifacts (Wallstrom et al., 2004). This time series was filtered to 65-115 Hz to further reduce the influence of brain activity on the extracted signal and enhance signal components related to muscular activity. Subsequently, the envelope of this signal was calculated using Hilbert transformation, and demeaned within each of the 5 concatenated eyes-closed recording blocks. Instead of directly thresholding this envelope, we applied a low pass filtered at 4 Hz to remove very transient peaks which are unlikely due to muscular activity, as proposed in the MNE-Python muscular artifact detection algorithm. Finally, the resulting signal was z-transformed and thresholded at $z > 2$ to identify periods of muscular activity based on extreme values in the distribution. Visual inspection of the annotations revealed that while this approach reliably detected muscular artifacts in subjects with pronounced contamination, in very clean recordings however, segments without visible artifacts were occasionally misclassified. To mitigate this issue, an additional constraint was imposed by retaining only those segments where the envelope of the first principal component exceeded 20 μV , thereby ensuring that only clear muscular activity was detected. Data was then segmented to one-second segments around the annotated data. If the length of a continuous annotation was shorter than one-second, one segment was extracted around the center of the annotation period. If an annotation lasted longer than

one-second, multiple non-overlapping one-second segments were extracted such that each segment contained at least 50% annotated muscular artifact data, thereby avoiding segments near annotation boundaries with minimal contamination.

For the EMG based muscular artifact detection, we first calculated the envelope of each of the three EMG channels using Hilbert transformation and subsequently applied a low pass filter of 4 Hz to this envelope to remove transient noisy peaks. Subsequently, this signal was z-transformed and thresholded to $z > 5$ in any of the three EMG channels (i.e., data was annotated as an artifact if activity in at least one of the EMG channels was above the threshold). Finally, the same segmentation around these annotations was applied as described above. Because the EMG channel on the forehead was also very sensitive for annotating muscular artifacts related to eye movements and blinks, we applied the same annotation procedure also to the HEOG and VEOG channels in the dataset. If any segment marked as muscular activity was also annotated as high EOG activity (either in the HEOG or the VEOG channel), the segment was not included for further analyses.